

OTT StreamQuest: A Personalized Recommender Engine

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Abstract—In an era marked by an explosion of exclusive and licensed content subscription services, the entertainment landscape is transforming. While consumers have more choices than ever before, they also face a growing challenge: managing their limited interests and ensuring that their subscriptions align with their viewing preferences. This paper explores the pressing need to create a more customer-centric entertainment ecosystem that simplifies subscription management, allowing individuals to curate a personalized entertainment experience without paying for unused services. The digital entertainment industry has witnessed an unprecedented proliferation of subscription-based platforms, each vying for a share of consumers' wallets. This proliferation often referred to as the "Streaming Wars" has led to an overwhelming array of content options, leaving many consumers grappling with subscription fatigue and content overload. Our study delves into the implications of this subscription fragmentation, emphasizing the necessity of rethinking the customer's role in this evolving landscape.

To design a customer-centric entertainment ecosystem, we advocate for the development of user-friendly tools and interfaces. These tools should empower individuals to effortlessly manage their subscriptions, enabling them to add or remove services in real time as their interests change. Personalization and recommendation algorithms can play a crucial role in helping users discover content that aligns with their preferences and dynamically adapts to their evolving tastes.

Keywords - Recommendation system; collaborative filtering; content-based filtering, KM-Slope-VU.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of entertainment consumption, the advent of Over-The-Top (OTT) streaming platforms has revolutionized how we engage with content in our fast-paced digital society. However, amidst the convenience and diversity offered by these platforms, a pressing challenge has emerged, particularly in bustling metropolitan cities — the phenomenon known as 'OTT fatigue.' A recent survey conducted by L.E.K. Consulting in the Media and Entertainment industry revealed that a more -

significant 18 percent of consumers across various age groups in the rapidly evolving landscape of entertainment consumption, the advent of Over-The-Top (OTT) streaming platforms has revolutionized how we engage with content in our fast-paced digital society. However, amidst the convenience and diversity offered by these platforms, a pressing challenge has emerged, particularly in bustling metropolitan cities — the phenomenon known as 'OTT fatigue.' A recent survey conducted by L.E.K. Consulting in the Media and Entertainment industry revealed that a significant 18 percent of consumers across various age groups are grappling with the overwhelming array of content choices, leading to decision overload and a palpable sense of weariness.

Acknowledging this challenge, our ambitious project embarks on a mission to redefine the very fabric of the OTT landscape. We propose an innovative solution that transcends the traditional OTT subscription model by seamlessly integrating cutting-edge data analytics and machine learning technologies. Our primary goal is to provide viewers with content recommendations that are not just tailored but finely tuned to their individual preferences.

This revolutionary approach does more than addressing the burden of decision fatigue; it aims to elevate user satisfaction and drive heightened engagement with the platform. In the paragraphs that follow, we will delve into the multifaceted features and strategies that make our solution a crucial step forward in addressing the evolving dynamics of entertainment consumption in the modern digital era. From cross-platform integration and augmented reality experiences to blockchain-based content authentication and green energy initiatives, our project aspires to set a new standard for personalized, engaging, and sustainable entertainment consumption. By leveraging advanced machine learning algorithms, our platform offers personalized recommendations that adapt to users' evolving tastes and preferences. This not only enhances the viewing experience but also ensures that users are consistently exposed to fresh, relevant content.

II. RELATED WORK

The work presented in [1] introduces an innovative approach to affective movie recommendations based on connotative features, specifically focusing on the shooting, and editing conventions used in films to convey emotional meaning. This unique system successfully predicts connotative values from audiovisual features, enabling precise recommendations of movie scenes that evoke similar emotional responses to a user's query. Remarkably, the proposed method eliminates the need for invasive data collection from users or dependence on others' emotional ratings, ensuring scalability and improved accuracy. One notable advantage lies in the system's reliance on connotative concepts, which are more universally agreed upon among users than individual emotional reactions, enhancing the accuracy of recommendations for individual users. Moreover, its non-obtrusive nature distinguishes it from traditional emotion analysis methods, as it doesn't require monitoring physiological signals or relying on users' self-reporting. However, the approach does have limitations, primarily being restricted to recommending movie scenes rather than entire movies, potentially limiting its applicability in certain scenarios. Additionally, while connotation provides a more objective representation of emotions, it remains subjective and may not fully capture the intricacies of human emotions.

The [2] proposal introduces a groundbreaking approach titled "Smart User Consumption Profiling: Incremental Learning-Based OTT Service Degradation." The primary focus is on proposing personalized service degradation policies through the innovative use of Incremental Learning (IL) and analysis of Over-The-Top (OTT) consumption behavior. A comprehensive evaluation of multiple algorithms has been conducted, revealing that Adaptive Random Forest and a combination of Leverage Bagging and ARF exhibit precision and recall rates exceeding an impressive 90 percent.

This research is particularly relevant for mobile network operators, offering real-world applicability that translates into improved overall performance, efficient resource utilization, and heightened user satisfaction. Notably, the proposed reference model stands as a pioneering effort in the field, emphasizing its significance in user consumption profiling and service management.

Despite its notable strengths, the approach does have some associated disadvantages. The computational complexity of certain IL algorithms, especially when handling large datasets, may pose challenges in practical implementations. Additionally, the personalized service degradation policies suggested by the model may trigger concerns among users about potential monitoring and control of their data usage, potentially impacting overall user satisfaction. Striking a balance between the benefits of personalized policies and addressing user privacy concerns will be crucial for the successful adoption of this innovative approach.

The [3] Genome offers a novel solution to challenges faced by traditional content-based collaborative filtering methods. Overcoming issues related to predicting user preferences and dealing with sparsity and cold start problems, the proposed algorithm introduces the innovative concept of content genome. This approach proves particularly effective for mass recommendation scenarios where many items need to be recommended to a diverse user base.

The methodology of the algorithm revolves around enhancing personalized recommendations through the incorporation of content characteristics. By utilizing a content genome matrix, the algorithm calculates genetic similarity between content items, significantly improving accuracy in similarity calculations. The introduction of a variable parameter (β) further fine-tunes the balance between genetic and content similarity. Real-world data evaluation validates the algorithm's performance, leading to continual refinement and optimization. In summary, this algorithm shows promise in providing more accurate and precise recommendations in scenarios requiring mass recommendation.

While the algorithm boasts several advantages, including improved precision and accuracy due to the incorporation of the content genome, it is not without its limitations. The effectiveness of the algorithm heavily relies on the careful selection of genes that accurately represent content characteristics. The selection of irrelevant or improper genes may lead to suboptimal recommendations. Additionally, the algorithm primarily focuses on content-based similarity, potentially overlooking valuable user-item interactions that could influence recommendations. This limitation may result in missing out on certain user preferences and reducing the overall recommendation quality. Despite these challenges, the algorithm presents a significant step forward in addressing the complexities of collaborative filtering in content recommendation systems.

The development and evaluation of a Personalized Real-Time Movie Recommendation System are presented in [4] featuring the Collaborative Filtering (CF) algorithm known as KM-Slope-VU. This algorithm operates on the premise that users sharing similar attributes, such as gender, age, and occupation, are likely to have similar movie preferences and ratings. Utilizing K-means clustering, the KM-Slope-VU algorithm groups users based on these profile characteristics. Additionally, the proposed Weighted Slope One-VU algorithm predicts user ratings by considering popularity differentials between items for virtual users pairwise. Additionally, the incorporation of the Weighted Slope One-VU algorithm, which accounts for popularity differentials, contributed to more robust and personalized movie recommendations. This research marks a significant stride in advancing recommendation systems

One of the notable advantages of the Weighted KM-Slope-VU approach lies in its efficiency and scalability compared to traditional matrix factorization-based algorithms. The authors implemented a practical evaluation through Movie Watch, a personalized movie recommendation site, allowing the collection of real-life user feedback on recommended movies. This real data provides a valuable assessment of the proposed algorithm's performance. The algorithm's efficiency for large datasets is further enhanced by the reduced virtual opinion leader-item matrix, reducing computational complexity.

However, the approach is not without its drawbacks. The use of only one virtual opinion leader per cluster may result in a slight loss of valuable information, potentially leading to slightly lower prediction accuracy compared to SVD and SVD++. Additionally, the accuracy of real feedback evaluation in Movie Watch may be affected by outdated movie data and limited data samples. Despite these challenges, the Personalized Real-Time Movie Recommendation System introduces an innovative approach with practical implications, offering a faster and scalable solution for movie recommendations.

The [5] introduces an analysis focused on determining user intent through domain keyword bases and matching questions with appropriate patterns. When a user poses a question, the system checks for matches with predefined patterns, proceeding with a targeted search based on the identified pattern. To enhance this process, segmentation is performed on the user's question using the LTP segmentation system, employing a comprehensive keyword base of 19120 food-related keywords. The advantages of this approach are evident in its precision, achieving an impressive 90.9%. This precision improvement is attributed to the integration of semantic recommendation technology, allowing the system to effectively handle situations where user queries may not be readily understood. However, the method does present certain challenges. Extracting patterns in domains where existing videos are not classified as expected poses a difficulty, impacting the quality of patterns and, subsequently, recommendation precision. Additionally, the system faces limitations when a question contains two or more keywords from a single domain, necessitating further consideration and refinement to address such scenarios.

Despite these challenges, the User Recommendation Based on Semantic Pattern demonstrates promising results in precision enhancement and the ability to navigate user queries where understanding may otherwise be challenging.

III. Proposed Personalized Movie Recommendation System

The project uses TMDB Api to fetch data about various movies and shows available on various Ott platform for basic training of the algorithm we have imported the data of about 10,000 movies with over 1 million ratings obtained from various users for the recommendation part of the project we

have used scikit-learn models like K- Means also with Cosine Similarity which will explain later and for the implementation of the Project we have used Django as our Backend Framework and for Frontend we have ReactJs keeping MySQL as our core Database and TMDB for API for live request for this application.

A. Dataset

The TMDB (The Movie Database) API is a web service that allows inventors to pierce and recoup information about pictures, television shows, and actors.

- It provides a wide range of data related to the entertainment industry. Then are some crucial points and features of the TMDB API penetrating the API.
- The API key is essential for making requests and authenticating your access to the data. API Endpoints the TMDB API provides colorful endpoints, each serving a specific purpose.
- Some common endpoints include Movie Information about pictures, including details like title, release date, and cast. television Details about television shows, including seasons, occurrences, and cast. Person Information about actors, directors, and other individuals involved in the entertainment industry.
- Search Allows you to search for pictures, television shows, and people. Request and Response Format Requests to the TMDB API are made using standard HTTP styles (GET, POST, etc.). Responses are generally in JSON format, making it easy to parse and integrate into operations. Authentication is needed for utmost API requests and is done using your API key.
- Rate Limiting the TMDB API has rate limiting to help abuse. Be sure to check the attestation for the specific rate limits grounded on your account type. Image API TMDB also offers an Image API that allows you to recoup movie and television show bills, backgrounds, and other images. Statistics The TMDB API provides some introductory statistics related to pictures and television shows, like fissionability scores and vote.

B. System's Architecture

The proposed Architecture encompasses a holistic approach that begins with the collection and analysis of user data to comprehensively understand their viewing behavior and content preferences. By harnessing this wealth of information, we aim to craft a more personalized entertainment experience for our users. To achieve this, we will develop a cutting-edge recommendation system powered by advanced machine learning algorithms, drawing from both content-based and collaborative filtering techniques. This system will sift through

the vast array of available content and present tailored recommendations to users, increasing the likelihood of them discovering content that aligns with their unique tastes.

Fig. 1. System Level Architecture

A detailed description of the project Architecture is given below.

- OTT Plans: The website will consist of plans ranging from various OTT Plan providers as per the user demands.
- Payment Gateway: Website is fully functional with a properly integrated payment gateway in this case we are using Razor Pay.
- Personalized Recommendation System: The website will be handling Realtime live data from TMDB API and will be providing content as well as collaborative based recommendation based on the user profile.
- Watch Along: Along with all the features the website will have its own video calling platform which can be used to connect and watch the desired movie / series along with friends.

1V. Algorithm Architecture

Fig. 2. Algorithm Architecture

In the initial phases while training the model while doing demographic analysis we take into consideration the weighted rating content which can help to analysis the trend of a particular movie on a long term which can we used for Trending Section.

Next, we use in Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) to create a matrix which gives us the frequency of occurrence or a word in that dataset which will form the base on which we will do our content-based recommendation. For content-based recommendation we need to find out the similarity between 2 or more movies. We will use cosine similarity to calculate a numerical value representing the similarity between two movies. We use the similar value of cosine because it is independent of amplitude and relatively easy and fast to calculate. Mathematically it is defined as:

$$\text{similarity} = \cos(\theta) = \frac{\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}}{\|\mathbf{A}\| \|\mathbf{B}\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}}$$

Fig. 3. Cosine Similarity Formula

Then using this sklearn's **linear kernel()** function we will take in the parameters we need that are required for us such as initially we took in just the title name and the movies consisting that same word were recommended this is not a good recommendation practice we took in the top 3 cast , the directors , the genre into consideration in our **get_recommendation ()** function and the parameter can be the title of the movie and the recommendations were satisfactory.

We can think that people will have similar interest in the movies and give similar ratings to the movies. Based on this theory, we developed the CF algorithm KM-Slope-VU, which uses K-means to divide users into different groups based on their personal data characteristics, and then all groups are generated. opinion leaders by calculating the average of the items. Moreover, we intuitively believe that historical information about the user's evaluation of the product is always relevant to their tastes and should therefore be used for the user group. Specifically, for each group, virtual opinion leaders rate each item on behalf of other users in the same group, and then the ratings of each virtual opinion leader are summed to estimate the data ratings of real users. That is, the original user project rating matrix is replaced by a simple virtual opinion manager-project rating matrix we took the SVD algorithm for this which is widely used for collaborative recommendation and it reduces the dimensions of the data to reduce noise in the existing dataset.

This means that the user-project matrix is compressed and the computational complexity is reduced. Please note that the main idea behind the traditional Slope One algorithm is to predict the user's item rating based on the difference between the scores of pairs of items. Based on this concept, the Weighted Slope One-VU concept works in a pair according to the intuitive principle of the popular difference between products for the virtual user; for example, to determine what the person likes. The product is compared with other products. One way to measure this difference is to subtract virtual users' average scores on the two items. In turn, this difference can be used to predict how users would rate one of the products, given their ratings on other products.

V. Implementation

Fig 4. Plan selection based on various platforms

Fig 9. Added a Trending section that displays all trending shows/movies today and current week

Fig 5. Discover movie list showing Top rated and Most Popular based on content available on platforms selected

Fig 10. Discover latest movies and TV shows based on genre, sort them based on preference

Fig 6. Details of content selected with an option for user to give their own

Fig 11. Watch trailers of all movies/shows available directly on the application

Fig 7. Content-based recommendation based on content selected for details

Fig 12. Cast information and official YouTube videos related to the movie/show directly available

Fig 8. Collaborative recommendation based on rating entered by user

Fig 13. WatchAlong feature that lets you create a watch party and lets you stream content

VI. Results and Discussion

A. Results

The RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) score is a measure used to evaluate the performance of our recommendation system. Regression situations where the output (a predicted scalar value) is compared with the true scalar value output for a particular data point are usually evaluated using RMSE. Therefore, use RMSE if you are just proposing a score (like a movie rating). This metric helps assess the accuracy of the recommendation system in predicting user preferences for content. For our situation, the mean Root Mean Square Error of 0.80 approx. is more than sufficient.

Fig 4. The squared differences between predicted and actual ratings are calculated for each movie, average of these squared differences is taken. Finally, the square root of this average is calculated to get the RMSE score.

B. Discussion

We have used RMSE as performance matrix and this means the lower the RMSE values the accurate the results in some cluster of the users data there might be users who have not watched or rated the moves and thus the RMSE value shoots up above 0.9 such as in cluster 5 this is why we used 5 cluster so that if any in accurate recommendation is made the other clusters can counter and the model the overcome the invaluable noise made by the made this makes our model robust and we achieve an average of 0.80 accuracy which is good considering our dataset when we move over to live data from API the error can be reduced to a great extent.

VII. Conclusion

The proposed system aims to improve the ongoing Ott based recommendation system by adding a touch of personalization where in a user driven data points drives the entire process apart from the traditional content-based recommendation Engine. The KM-Slope-VU Collaborative Filtering algorithm utilizes the collective wisdom of users in the same cluster to enhance movie recommendations. It Encompasses a holistic approach that begins with the collection and analysis of user data.

To comprehensively understand their viewing behavior and content preferences. By harnessing this wealth of information, we aim to craft a more personalized entertainment experience for our users. To achieve this, we will develop a cutting-edge recommendation system powered by advanced machine learning algorithms, drawing from both content-based and collaborative filtering techniques. This system will sift through the vast array of available content and present tailored recommendations to users, increasing the likelihood of them discovering content that aligns with their unique tastes.

Furthermore, the integration of this personalized recommendation system into our platform will be seamless, ensuring that users can easily access content that resonates with their interests. To guarantee its effectiveness, the system will undergo rigorous testing, monitoring, and user feedback analysis. Our commitment to continuous improvement means that the recommendation system will evolve in step with changing user preferences and emerging content trends, ultimately enhancing the overall user experience and reinforcing our dedication to a customer-centric entertainment ecosystem that adapts to users' ever-evolving needs and desires.

VIII. Future Work

Looking ahead, the personalized recommendation system, built on the KM-Slope-VU Collaborative Filtering algorithm, is poised to evolve in several directions, expanding its effectiveness and adaptability to changing user preferences and technological advancements. One avenue for development lies in integrating emerging technologies like natural language processing (NLP) and computer vision, enabling the analysis of user-generated content and social interactions to glean deeper insights into individual tastes. Furthermore, advancements in data analytics and machine learning could allow the system to dynamically adjust recommendations based on evolving user behavior and content trends. Additionally, with the expansion of the digital entertainment ecosystem across various platforms and devices, future iterations could prioritize seamless cross-platform integration, ensuring users can access personalized suggestion effortlessly and adding on more plans and service providers.

IX. References

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